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Glossary

CCEM	Consultative Committee for Electricity and Magnetism
CF	Calibration factor
CRV	Comparison Reference Value
DCTM	Direct comparison transfer method
DoE	Degrees of Equivalence
DPS	Device under test power sensor
HF	High frequency
EU	European Union
GUM	Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement
MPS	Monitor power sensor
NMI	National Metrology Institute
RF	Radio Frequency
SM	Substitution method
SPS	Standard power sensor
TEM	Transversal Electromagnetic (e.g., wave)
VBPSC	VNA Based Power Sensor Calibration
VBPSCM	VNA-based calibration method
VNA	Vector Network Analyser

Summary

This report summarises the work performed within the project 22RPT04 RFMicrowave2 (Development of RF and microwave metrology capability II), a EURAMET project running between May 2023 and April 2026, in particular the experience gained with the new method for the calibration factor of RF power sensors using a vector network analyser (VNA). The method has been implemented in several participants' laboratories and will be used in the future as an alternative to the classical direct comparison method.

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For further details about the RFMicrowave 2 project see the project website <https://rfmwii.cmi.gov.cz/>

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1. Introduction

RF power sensor calibration is one of the essential measurements in RF and microwave metrology [1]. There are many methods, such as the substitution method (SM), the direct comparison transfer method (DCTM), and the VNA-based calibration method (VBPSCM), that can be used for reliable and accurate power sensor calibration.

According to the SM, measurements are performed by connecting a power sensor with a known calibration factor (CF) (standard power sensor—SPS) value and a power sensor with an unknown CF (device under test power sensor—DPS) value to the RF signal source. This method assumes that the RF signal source output has the same power level when the SPS and DPS are connected to the RF signal source. The DPS and SPS are connected directly to the RF signal source for the measurements, unless a characterized adapter or an attenuator is used at the output of the RF signal source. Suppose the reflection coefficient values of the RF signal sources are not measured vectorially. In that case, an impedance mismatch cannot be fully taken into account in the DPS's CF calculation in this method [2,3].

The SM assumes that the RF signal source output has almost the same value when measuring the DPS and the SPS. This situation is impossible because the RF signal source output can change over time. The DCTM was developed to eliminate the error due to this assumption. In this method, a new different power sensor called a monitor power sensor (MPS) monitors the output of the RF signal source while measuring both the SPS and DPS power. When the operator connects the SPS to the measurement system, the monitor power measurement (P_{mS}) is performed together with the measured SPS power (P_{STD}). When the operator connects the DPS to the measurement system, the DPS power (P_{DUT}) is measured simultaneously with the monitor power (P_{mD}) measurement. A well-characterized power splitter is used at the output of the RF signal source. The DPS's CF value is calculated by using the reflection coefficient of the DPS, the reflection coefficient of the SPS, the reflection coefficient of the power splitter, the four measured power values (P_{DUT} , P_{STD} , P_{mS} , P_{mD}), and the CF value of the SPS. Thus, it is possible to take into account the impedance mismatches in the DCTM, which cannot be fully calculated in the SM [4–7].

To calculate the DPS's CF value in the SM, the operator should measure the reflection coefficient of the output port of the RF signal source and the reflection coefficient of the DPS. To calculate the DPS's CF value in the DCTM, the operator should measure the DPS's reflection coefficient and power splitter's reflection coefficient. The reflection coefficient of the SPS is taken from the certificate of the SPS in both methods. The operator should use the VNA for reflection coefficient measurements of the DPS in both methods.

The VNA includes an RF signal source, a power splitter or directional coupler, and at least two power sensors used for the reflected and transmitted power measurements. These devices in the VNA show that the VNA contains most of the devices needed by the DCTM, which is the method used to determine the CF value of the DPS. The VNA-based CF determination method (VBPSCM) was developed based on the idea of simultaneously measuring the reflection coefficients and performing the necessary measurements for the DCTM, which is necessary to calculate the DPS's CF using the VNA [8–10].

The SM and DCTM are both well-known power sensor calibration methods used in the metrological domain. On the other hand, the VBPSCM is a newer method and has recently been utilized in some new R&D projects (EMPIR 20IND03 Futurecom) [11], as well as in some national metrology institutes, such as KRISS, South Korea, and TUBITAK UME, Türkiye [8,9]. The VBPSCM is a preferred method since the VNA has a better measurement capability and has fewer connection requirements for measurement devices [9].

All of these methods need an SPS and a DPS to be calibrated. These power sensors are compared during the calibration processes. At the end of the power sensor calibration process for each calibration method, the operator should carry out a parameter known as the calibration factor (CF). The CF is the ratio of the output DC power of the power sensor (P_{ind}) over the incident RF power of the sensor (P_{in}). This ratio is given in Equation (1):

$$CF = \frac{P_{ind}}{P_{in}} M \tag{1}$$

where M is the impedance mismatch of the RF connectors.

In this report, VBPSM is presented along with the milestones of the VBPSM, the potential application errors of the VBPSM, the rules that should be considered while connecting to the device while measuring with the VNA, the factors to consider while developing the control software for the VNA, and the power meter control are explained. After the power sensor calibration measurements using the VBPSM are shown, the model function components to be used in the uncertainty calculations and the uncertainty calculation examples according to the GUM Law of Propagation method are also shared in this report. Finally, the pros and cons of the VBPSM compared to the former methods are discussed. Additionally, the result of the planned comparison at the 22RPT04 RfMicrowave 2 project is presented under the Experimental Results and Analysis of VBPSM section including the comparison participants' feedbacks.

2. Requirements of VNA-Based Power Sensor Calibration Method (VBPSM)

The use of the VNA provides convenience in implementing the VBPSM, but it needs more attention since the VNA is such a complicated device. The requirements of the VBPSM can be given in three subsections, such as the measurement setup, the software, and the measurement process.

2.1. Requirements of Measurement Setup

Basic power sensor calibration setups of DCTM and VBPSM are given in Figure 1 and Figure 2, respectively [4–7]. In Figure 1, there are three power sensors and proper power meters. The STD power sensor is reference, the DUT power sensor is the sensor to be calibrated, and the MON power sensor is the monitoring sensor in the setup.

Figure 1. Power sensor calibration setup with DCTM.

Figure 2. Power sensor calibration setup with VBPSM.

A power splitter separates the output of the RF signal source power into two lines. In Figure 2, the A1 power sensor monitors the transmitted power according to the DCTM. When measuring with the DPS, the A1 and R1 power sensors are used to calculate the reflection coefficient when measuring with the DPS.

In the VBPSM, there is no need for the external MPS for monitoring the signal generator's output. There is an internal power sensor (A1 in Figure 2) in the superheterodyne receiver system of the VNA, which is used as the MPS in the VBPSM. The D1 directional coupler in Figure 2 is used in the VBPSM instead of the power splitter in the DCTM. So, there are fewer RF connection requirements in the VBPSM when compared with the DCTM. The SPS and DPS are connected to the VNA port in the VBPSM while also connected to the power splitter in the DCTM. The CF of the DPS (CF_{DUT}) is calculated in the VBPSM using Equation (2) [5,8]:

$$CF_{DUT} = CF_{STD} \cdot \frac{P_{DUT}}{P_{STD}} \cdot \frac{Pm_S}{Pm_D} \cdot \frac{|1 - \Gamma_{DUT} \cdot \Gamma_{PV}|^2}{|1 - \Gamma_{STD} \Gamma_{PV}|^2} \quad (2)$$

where CF_{STD} is the CF of SPS; P_{DUT} and P_{STD} are the power measured with the DPS and the SPS, respectively; Pm_S is the power measured by A1 in Figure 2 when the SPS is connected; Pm_D is the power measured by A1 in Figure 2 when the DPS is connected; Γ_{DUT} is the reflection coefficient of the DPS; Γ_{STD} is the reflection coefficient of the SPS; and Γ_{PV} is the reflection coefficient of the VNA port, which is used to connect the SPS and DPS.

2.2. Requirements of Software

The CF value of the power sensor is dependent on the frequency ($CF = f(\text{frequency})$). To obtain the CF values, the operator should perform the measurements at all frequency ranges. And to obtain the proper DPS CF values, power measurements should be repeated at least ten times at each frequency. A software is required for these repetitive measurements. Software can perform repeated measurements to reduce operator error and measurement time. Software controls the

RF signal generator and power meters in the DCTM and the SM while performing the measurements at the same time. The software controls the VNA and the power meters in the VBPSM as well. Also, the algorithm given in the Equation (2) has been utilized in the software to determine the CF of the DPS.

In this project, the software that controls the VNA and the power meters was developed using the C# programming language with the collaboration of TUBITAK, SPARK, and METU [8]. A GPIB/USB adapter was used to communicate between the PC and the measurement devices. The VNA and power meter were controlled using the SCPI codes in the software.

2.3. Requirements of Measurement Process

The following procedures should be applied while applying the VBPSM:

- The operator should set the frequency and power levels for the ranges that the VNA would measure. The operator should select the calibration kit to determine the error terms according to the frequency range and connector type to be used.
- The VNA must learn the error terms at the correct frequencies and at the correct power level by using the calibration kit.
- The power meters to which the SPS and DPS will be connected must be reset and pre-calibrated (zeroing and calibrating at 1 mW) before the measurement.
- A suitable physical interface connection, such as GPIB, that can control all devices is selected between the VNA, the power meter, and the PC. The operator should check the communication between the PC and measurement devices using the physical interface and the interface's software.
- A VBPSM software that can control the VNA and the power meter should be used to perform measurements. The operator should enter the frequencies selected in the step of learning the error terms of the VNA into the VBPSM software. The operator should ensure that the frequency steps in the VNA and VBPSM software are the same.
- The VBPSM software should have a user interface that can enter the waiting time intervals between frequencies, the repetition number for power readings at each selected frequency, and the time after the turning on of the RF signal source power.
- It is necessary to note that the applied power from the VNA's port should be within the DPS's and SPS's measurement limits.
- The SPS should be connected to the VNA's port, and the VBPSM software should measure the SPS's power. At the same time, the software should measure the MPS's power too.
- The SPS should be removed from the VNA's port, and then the DPS should be reconnected to the VNA's port. The VBPSM software should measure the DPS's power and the MPS's power. The software should simultaneously measure the DPS's reflection coefficient with the DPS's power measurement.
- The CF of the DPS can be calculated using some parameters. In order to calculate the DPS's CF value, the following parameters should be used, except for the reflection coefficient and power values measured in the previous steps:
 - The calibration factor of the SPS from the SPS certificate;
 - The reflection coefficients of the SPS taken from the SPS certificate;
 - The source mismatch error parameter of the connected port of the VNA. This value should be taken from the saved calibration of the VNA (from error terms as source mismatch error).

Flow graph of the software is given in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Required software flow graph for VBPSM

3. Potential Errors of VBPSM and Suggested Solutions

Regarding their frequencies and dynamic measuring range, VNAs are the most complex and expensive instruments used in microwave measurements. A VNA contains two RF signal sources and at least two or four RF power sensors according to the number of ports, directional couplers, and RF switches internally. Since a PC mainly controls the VNA, a PC has been added inside the new-generation VNA instead of the computing unit included by the manufacturers. If an external computer controls the VNA, the external computers should communicate with the VNA's computer and the VNA's sub-devices inside, such as signal generators and power sensors [12,13].

RF power sensors are essential devices used in basic power measurement. RF power sensors should be used according to the operating frequency and power range [14,15]. RF power meters are indicators that show the value measured by the RF power sensor. RF power meters can show incorrect values when controlled by the wrong coding software or timing [14,15].

It is possible to have many errors if the software is not well-configured in the VBPSM. The VBPSM software controls the VNA and the two power meters by the PC. In addition, avoiding mistakes when working with such sensitive measuring devices (VNA) is impossible.

Errors may occur if the abovementioned requirements are not covered in the VBPSM process. Errors were categorized into two categories, such as "Measurement Errors" and "Calculation Errors", in this study.

3.1. The Measurement Errors

Due to the incorrect reflection coefficient reading of DPS:

The VNA frequency steps and the frequency steps given in the developed software must be the same. If the frequencies are out of sync, false reflection coefficients will be read at the wrong frequencies using the error terms determined by the VNA calibration. When calibrating the VNA, if the operator enters only the frequency number for the start–end frequencies and the frequencies between, the same steps must be defined in the PC control software. Also, if the operator determines the frequency segment sweep during VNA calibration, the operator should select the same frequency steps in the PC software. The problem of reading the wrong reflection coefficient caused by this situation can be solved by reading the frequency steps of the VNA by software.

Due to the incorrect power reading by SPS or DPS:

In case the frequencies need to be in sync between the PC software and the VNA, the PC software reads the power at the wrong power meter frequencies. The PC software sends the wrong frequency to the VNA, and the software sets the VNA's RF source to the wrong frequency. For this reason, the power value readings will be wrong. The software can solve this problem by reading the frequency steps from the VNA and sending the correct frequency command to the VNA before power reading.

Due to the incorrect power reading by the SPS power meter or DPS power meter:

When the power meters are not set to the 100% CF values at the beginning of the measurement, the DPS and SPS will read incorrect values. In the VBPSM, the software calculates the CF of the DPS by using the CF of the STD power sensor. In order to correct the CF of the DPS calculation, the power meter correction factor should be 100%. Such issues can be identified and resolved by the experience and qualification of the operators.

Due to the VNA's power output instability:

If the output power of the used VNA shows any noticeable fluctuations, and could not be considered stable, the power applied to the DPS and SPS results in wrong power application and reading from SPS and DPS. In order to correct this situation, operator should consider the VNA's port output power stability for VBPSM method.

Due to the incorrect power read timing (1):

After the software sets the RF signal source of the VNA to the desired power, it can give the desired power for a particular time. When reading from the power meter connected to the DPS or SPS is performed after the power-on period of the VNA RF signal has elapsed, the software will read the incorrect power values. In order to eliminate this problem, the operator should know the VNA operation as well, and the developer should develop the PC control software according to the VNA's operation specs.

Due to the incorrect power read timing (2):

After the software turns on the power at the VNA signal source, it is necessary to take a measurement with the power meter after the power level has stabilized. The operator should determine the VNA's signal source stabilization time before the measurement and enter it into the developed software. The operator can also solve this problem by knowing the VNA's specs.

Due to the incorrect reflection coefficient reading of the SPS:

Although it is possible to measure the reflection coefficient of the SPS with the VNA during the SPS power measurement, it is not necessary. Software developers can add the reflection coefficient of the SPS reading into the software. The operator can use only this to check the connector of the SPS. If the software uses the new reading reflection coefficient of the SPS to calculate the CF of the DPS, incorrect metrological traceability transfer will occur. In order to correct the transfer to traceability, the software uses the reflection coefficients from the last certificate of the SPS.

3.2. The Calculation Errors

Using the wrong reflection coefficient of the SPS:

The reflection coefficient is not constant and changes because of the wear out of the connectors over time. When the software uses the wrong reflection coefficient of the SPS, the software calculates incorrect CF values of the DPS. The software developer should be careful to enter the right reflection coefficient using the CF of the DPS.

Using the wrong uncertainty of the reflection coefficient of the DPS:

When calculating the CF uncertainty of the DPS, the operator or the software should use the correct uncertainty of the reflection coefficients of the DPS and SPS. Otherwise, the operator or the software will miscalculate the CF uncertainty of the DPS. When the operator or the software perform the reflection coefficient measurement and the power reading of the DPS separately, the uncertainty calculation problem will not happen. If the developed software calculates the uncertainty of the reflection coefficient at the same time as the measurement, there will be no problem.

Unknown uncertainty of VNA's source mismatch error:

While it is sufficient to know the source mismatch error parameter of the connected port of the VNA to calculate the impedance mismatch, the operator cannot calculate the uncertainty value of the source mismatch error. It is suggested that the operator can use the generic uncertainty values of the reflection coefficient of the VNA and the calibration kit pairs as assumptions.

4. Experimental Results and Analysis of VBPSM

Two experimental measurements in which possible errors are detected, and solution proposals are determined are presented as examples in this study. They are given below;

- Method validation experiment
- Comparison experiment

4.1 Method validation experiment

Measurements were performed by the two different measurement setups given in Figure 2. The technical specifications of the VNA, power meter, power sensors, and mechanical calibration kits for the measurement setups are given in Table 1.

In the first measurement setup, the operator selected the frequencies according to the DPS specs, which were between 10 MHz and 26.5 GHz and a 0 dBm power level. The selected frequencies were 10, 50, 100, 500, 1000, 3000, 5000, 7000, 9000, 10000, 12000, 14000, 15000, 16000, 18000, 20000, 22000, 24000, and 26500 in MHz. The operator selected an SPS similar to the DPS, and it has a metrological traceability chain. The software performed each power measurement in one second at each frequency step.

Table 1. The equipment used in the measurement setups.

Equipment	Model	Measurement Range	Setup number
SPS1	N8485A	10 MHz–26.5 GHz	First
DPS1	N8485A	10 MHz–26.5 GHz	
Power Meters1	N1914A	–70 dBm–+44 dBm	
VNA1	N5235A	10 MHz–50 GHz	
Mechanical Calibration Kit1	85052B	DC–26.5 GHz	
SPS2	8482A	10 MHz–4.2 GHz	Second
DPS2	8482A	10 MHz–4.2 GHz	
Power Meters2	N1914A	–70 dBm–+44 dBm	
VNA2	N5225A	10 MHz–50 GHz	
Mechanical Calibration Kit2	85054D	10 MHz–18 GHz	

Before starting the measurements, the operator kept the power sensors in ambient conditions of 23 ± 3 °C and 45 ± 15 %rh (relative humidity). These conditions make the power sensors reach thermal equilibrium. The operator used an 8 lb.-in torque for the tightening of the RF connectors. The timing parameters of the measurements were determined as follows:

- Waiting time between frequencies: one second;
- Waiting time for each power measurement: one second;
- Number of measurements at each frequency: ten.

In the second measurement setup, the operator selected the frequencies according to the DPS specs, which were between 10 MHz and 4.2 GHz and a 0 dBm power level. The selected frequencies were 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500, 600, 700, 800, 900, 1000, 2000, 3000, and 4000 in MHz. The operator selected an SPS similar to the DPS, and it has a metrological traceability chain. The software performed each power measurement in one second at each frequency step. Before starting the measurements, the operator kept the power sensors in ambient conditions of 23 ± 1 °C and 45 ± 15 %rh (relative humidity). The operator used a 12 lb.-in torque for the tightening of the RF connectors. The operator used the same timing parameters for the measurements as in the first measurement setup.

Measurements and calculations were performed using the developed VBPSM software.

While taking the measurements using the developed software at the frequencies and power levels, the operator recorded the results manually for software validation.

The CF values of the DPS calculated by the VBPSM for each measurement setup and the CF values of the DPS from previous certificates were compared in this study. Previous certificate CF values and VBPSM CF values of the DPS are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4 for the first and

second measurement setups, respectively. It can be seen that the CF of the DPS from the previous certificate are in harmony with the CF of the DPS obtained using the VBPSM.

Figure 3. Comparison of DUT PS (N8485A) CF values for first measurement setup.

Figure 4. Comparison of DUT PS (8482A) CF values for second measurement setup.

The VBPSM software calculated the uncertainty of the DPS according to the GUM Bayesian method [16,17]. The uncertainty calculated by the VBPSM and the uncertainty of the previous certificate of the DPS were compared, and the uncertainties are given in Figures 5 and 6 according to the measurements setups. Figure 6 shows a big difference in the uncertainty values between

the VBPSM and the previous certificate values. Since the last calibration of the 8482A DPS was performed using the primary power sensor standard, the previous certificate's uncertainty values were relatively lower.

Figure 5. Comparison of uncertainties of DUT PS (N8485A) CF values for first measurement setup.

Figure 6. Comparison of uncertainties of DUT PS (8482A) CF values for second measurement setup.

4.2 Project comparison experiment

An experimental comparison of power sensor calibration using Vector Network Analyser was planned among the partners of the EMP (European Partnership on Metrology) project. This inter-laboratory comparison was part of the project “Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II” (22RPT04 ‘RFMicrowave2’).

5 (five) participants from the “22RPT04 RFMicrowave2” project were involved in the comparison. The procedure followed a technical protocol prepared by TÜBİTAK UME, which was agreed upon by all participants [18].

The comparison was carried out by measuring the Calibration Factors (CF) of the travelling standards, which was an Keysight- N type / N8481A and Keysight - 3.5 mm / U2063XA. Measurements were done at five different frequencies: 50 MHz, 1 GHz, 10 GHz, 15 GHz, 18 GHz for N type power sensor and 50 MHz, 1 GHz, 10 GHz, 20 GHz and 26.5 GHz for 3.5 mm power sensor. The travelling standards were provided by SPARK. TÜBİTAK UME was responsible to monitoring standard performance before and after the circulation and the evaluation and reporting of the comparison results. The developed software by METU was used in this comparison to VBPSC method to be applied. This software has capability for CF uncertainty calculations according to Law of Propagation (LoP) and Monte Carlo Simulations (MCS) methods. Measurements were carried out at five different frequencies for the Calibration Factor in this comparison, in accordance with the Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM).

Each participant has gained the capability for the VBPSC by participating in this experimental comparison. Comparison participants are SPARK, CMI, GUM, TRESKAL and TÜBİTAK. Each participant has used their own VNA and reference power sensor to compare the travelling standard and shared their measurement results with the pilot participant (TÜBİTAK).

The participants' the calibration factor values and their LoP uncertainties are given in Table 2 and Table 3.

CF values of the participants with Calibration Reference Values (X_{ref}) are given in Figure 7 and Figure 8 for this comparison.

Experiences of the comparison participants are given in “Discussion” chapter of this report.

Table 2. Calibration Factors and their LoP uncertainties of the comparison participants for N Type power sensor

Labs	TÜBİTAK UME		SPARK		CMI		GUM		Trescal		Reference Value	
	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	$u(CF)$ (k=1)
50 MHz			0.9982	0.0027	0.9980	0.0060	0.9994	0.0054	0.9970	0.0090	0.9983	0.0044
1 GHz	0.9932	0.0059	0.9925	0.0053	0.9920	0.0080	0.9924	0.0054	0.9930	0.0090	0.9926	0.0056
10 GHz	0.966	0.012	0.9685	0.0068	0.969	0.015	0.9689	0.0072	0.975	0.013	0.9691	0.0083
15 GHz	0.9691	0.0079	0.9668	0.0081	0.970	0.020	0.9678	0.0088	0.961	0.018	0.9676	0.0089
18 GHz	0.971	0.013	0.977	0.010	0.969	0.019	0.976	0.012	0.977	0.018	0.975	0.012

Table 3. Calibration Factors and their LoP uncertainties of the comparison participants for 3.5 mm power sensor

Labs	TÜBİTAK UME		SPARK		CMI		GUM		Trescal		Reference Value	
	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	CF	U (k=2)	y	$u(y)$ (k=1)
50 MHz			0.9945	0.0030	0.9900	0.0080	1.009	0.030	0.9830	0.0080	0.998	0.0044
1 GHz	1.078	0.017	1.0763	0.0087	1.063	0.011	1.08	0.032	1.0550	0.0090	1.067	0.010
10 GHz	1.087	0.020	1.087	0.013	1.063	0.022	1.084	0.033	1.0610	0.0200	1.078	0.017
20 GHz	1.021	0.025	1.017	0.017	1.015	0.034	1.031	0.034	1.011	0.038	1.019	0.023
26.5 GHz	0.978	0.025			0.975	0.033	0.984	0.034	0.972	0.050	0.978	0.033

0.05 GHz

1 GHz

10 GHz

15 GHz

Figure 7. CF graphs for N Type comparison standard (Model: N8481A SN:MY54350008) with CRV (Xref) and uncertainty of CRV

Figure 8. CF graphs for 3.5 mm comparison standard (Model: U2063XA SN:MY58000117) with CRV (Xref) and uncertainty of CRV

4.3 Individual experimental comparison at Trescal

One of the project partners, Trescal, performed an individual experimental comparison, in order to compare the VBPC software outputs with manual measurement outputs. The equipment used at Trescal is given in Table 4.

The manual measurements were carried out in the traditional way, comparing the travelling standards with the reference power sensors using a power splitter.

Trescal CF measurement results are given in Figure 9 and Figure 10 with uncertainty values.

Table 4. Equipment used with VBPC experiment in Trescal for 3.5 mm power sensor

Quipment	Model and Serial Number	Remarks
3.5 mm	Hewlett Packard 11792A Sensor Module, sn. 2124A01488	At VBPC Software
N-Type, Initial	Hewlett Packard 8481A Power Sensor, sn. 3318A91662	At VBPC Software
N-Type	Hewlett Packard 8481A Power Sensor, sn. MY41096355	At VBPC Software
Power Meter	Hewlett Packard E4419A, sn. GB36430157	At VBPC Software
VNA	Keysight E5080B ENA Network Analyzer, sn. MY59202928	At VBPC Software
Power Meter	Agilent N1914A Power Meter, sn. MY53520001	At VBPC Software
Cal Kit	Hewlett Packard 85052C, 3.5mm, sn. 3101A00258	At VBPC Software
Load	Wiltron 26N50 Load, +Open/Short, sn. 203135	At VBPC Software
N Type, Manual	Rohde & Schwarz NRP18T Thermal Power Sensor (N-type)	At Manual Measurement
3.5 mm, Manual	Rohde & Schwarz NRP33T Thermal Power Sensor (3.5mm)	At Manual Measurement
Power viewer	Readout of these reference power sensors via Rohde & Schwarz Power Viewer	At Manual Measurement

The different uncertainties between Initial VBPC and VBPC measurement results are mainly due to the fact that the calibration uncertainties from the certificates for the reference power sensors was entered into the software, rather than the full combined uncertainties for the subsequent use of these sensors - Initial VBPC was basically a test run.

Furthermore, following these Initial VBPC measurements the parameter settings in the software (waiting times, number of repetitions) were changed, to improve the measurements.

This clearly improved the agreement between the VBPC and the manual results, apart from the 50 MHz result for the Keysight U2063XA Power Sensor, where the expected improvement resulted in difference of 1 %CF instead (for this single run at least). However, the large difference at 1 GHz and 10 GHz between VBPC and manual measurements for the Keysight U2063XA Power Sensor remains a mystery.

Since the used Agilent N1914A Power Meter is not equipped with an USB port, the measurements of the Keysight U2063XA Power Sensor were carried out using the Keysight BenchVue software.

For this to work the BenchVue software had to be shut down during the VBPSC measurements, so it was not possible to observe the BenchVue software parameter settings during the measurements.

Figure 9. CF graphs for N Type Power Sensor (Model: N8481A SN:MY54350008) at Trescal experimental comparison

Figure 10. CF graphs for 3.5 mm Power Sensor (Model: U2063XA SN:MY58000117) at Trescal experimental comparison

5. Discussion

The applicability of the VBPSM has been demonstrated experimentally, and the results obtained from the application are given in this report.

In this project, the VBPSM was tested with the developed software for different devices and different measurement conditions. It was observed that successful results were obtained when measurements were made by taking into account possible errors.

A lot of experience has been gained during software development and experimental work. From this experience, we summarized the possible errors that could happen while applying the VBPSM, as follows:

- Errors due to the incorrect reflection coefficient reading of the DPS;
- Errors due to the incorrect power reading by the SPS or DPS;
- Errors due to the incorrect power reading by the SPS power meter or the DPS power meter;
- Errors due to the incorrect power read timing;
- Errors due to the incorrect reflection coefficient of the SPS being used in the calculation;
- Errors due to the incorrect uncertainty of the reflection coefficient of the DPS being used in the calculation;
- Errors due to the assumption of the uncertainty of the VNA's port in the calculation.

Some advantages of the VBPSM have been determined in this study. The advantages of the VBPSM are given as follows:

- To calculate the CF of DPS, both reflection coefficient measurements and power measurements should be performed with the power sensor to be calibrated (DPS). The VNA can perform these measurements at the same time.
- The power sensor calibration's duration can be decreased by using the VNA. It is possible to calibrate the power sensor as fast as the measurement speed of the VNA.
- There will be no need to use an external power splitter. Thus, the potential impedance mismatch components will be reduced by using the VNA.
- An operator who can use a VNA will also have the ability to calibrate the power sensor.

Although it seems like a disadvantage, the following conditions must be applied in the VBPSM's application:

- The VNA and the power meter have to be controlled with software. To perform an automatic measurement, a developed software should be used, or a software should be developed.
- The frequency steps determined before, the measurement of the VNA, and the frequency steps of control software must be synchronous.
- Before power sensor calibration, it is necessary to determine the error terms of the VNA and the pre-measurement settings (zero + cal) of the power sensor and power meter.

The organized experiment comparison and the participants' feedback are valuable for the improvement of the VBPSM method.

The main points of the collected from the participants' feedback can be summarized as follows.

- Software could be more user friendly if it would be improvement.
- VNA-PC communication driver could be more flexible with different GPIB adapters and different VNA types compatibility.
- Uncertainty calculation of the measured calibration factor could be separately for user friend software.
- The components of the calculated uncertainty could be presented with their percentage values to analyze the contribution the uncertainty component to the combined uncertainty.

6. Conclusions

In this report, the VNA-based power sensor calibration method (VBPSM) was introduced, and the requirements of the VBPSM were specified. Potential sources of error and their suggested

solutions in the VBPSM were also given in this report to guide those who want to conduct similar studies. The advantages and disadvantages of the VBPSM were also given in this report.

A software that controls the VNA and power meters was developed on the C# platform with the collaboration of TUBITAK, SPARK, and METU. In this study, the software validation was performed using manual measurement as well.

The developed software was used for experimental measurements with two different device setups. The CF values of the DPS obtained with the VBPSM software and the previous certificate values of the DPS were compared in this study. Measurement uncertainties were also calculated using software according to the GUM Bayesian method. The uncertainties calculated by the software and the uncertainties of the previous certificates were compared in this study as well. It was shown that the previous certificate CF data and the uncertainty of the CF are in harmony with the CF data and the uncertainty obtained using the VBPSM.

It is possible to obtain faster results in future studies, considering the solution suggestions for the possible errors determined in this project.

Finally, an inter-laboratory experimental comparison for the activity "A.1.2.6 RF Power Sensor Calibration with Vector Network Analyzer" has been conducted with the project partners [18]. Through this comparison, the project partners have gained the capability to perform VNA-based power sensor calibration. The comparison results showed that the VBPSM method is suitable to be used by microwave calibration laboratories.

The fact that the software developed for the VBPSM method is more modular, and that uncertainty calculations are performed separately outside the software rather than within it, is considered to be a more user-friendly solution that will help in the application of the VBPSM method in future studies.

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